

MEMCAT

Membrane-assisted Ethylene Synthesis over Nanostructured Tandem Catalysts

HORIZON EUROPE GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER: 101130047

Start date of project: 01/05/2024

Duration: 4 years

D5.1 Website and project logo information with also social media links

Call identifier	HORIZON-EIC-2023-PATHFINDEROPEN-01-01	
Deliverable:	D5.1 Website and project logo information with also social media links	
Work Package:	WP5 Dissemination and Exploitation	
Due date:	30/06/2024	
Submission date:	28/06/2024	
Organisation Responsible of Deliverable:	INL	
Version	1.1	
Author name(s):	Nuria Barros (INL)	
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Type:	<input type="checkbox"/>	R – Report
	<input type="checkbox"/>	Websites, patents filling, etc.
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	O – Other: DEC
	<input type="checkbox"/>	E – Ethics
Dissemination level:	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PU - Public
	<input type="checkbox"/>	SEN - Sensitive limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement

Version	DATE	Changes	CHECKED	APPROVED
V1	26-06-2024	First Version	Simona Scoppa	Nuria Barros
V2	28-06-2024	Final Version	Simona Scoppa	Nuria Barros

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1. Summary

This document describes the website, the project logo and the social media channels developed for the MemCat project at month 2 (June 2024). This deliverable has been prepared by INL, in collaboration with 1CUBE, and is written in the framework of WP5. Dissemination and Exploitation.

2. Website

The MemCat project website has been created on month 1 by partner 1CUBE and is online in the following link: <https://www.memcatproject.eu>. The website has been designed with a user-friendly configuration to improve the user experience and provide an easy access to all the key information about the project, including project information, partners' description, results and contact information.

The main objective is to increase awareness of the project's objectives and main results among scientists, the general public and potential industries.

With a vertical scroll down structure, the website is composed by six main sections (see top-right tabs in the figure below): "Home", "About", "News", "Events", "Project Results", "Dissemination" and "Contact". The content of the website is intended to provide key information about the project to potential stakeholders, to relevant European and related research initiatives, to the public in general and to attract the interest of the media channels.

Figure 1. MemCat website

2.1 Homepage

The “Homepage” section provides a general description of the MemCat project, the latest updates, and an overview of the other website sections. Contact emails are also included.

Additionally, this section will feature a form for visitors to submit their email addresses and subscribe to MemCat newsletters.

Figure 2. MemCat website Homepage

2.2 About

A detailed description of the research goals within MemCat project is displayed under the “About” section (Figure 3), as well as descriptions of each of the entities conforming the MemCat team and its role in the project (Figure 4).

MemCat targets to deliver a proof-of-concept for the direct conversion of CO₂ to ethylene by realizing tandem catalysts, which through nanostructuring will allow for consecutive CO₂-to-methanol and methanol-to-ethylene conversions to occur in the same operational window.

A fundamental understanding of the parameters governing the reactions will be gained through detailed operando studies of the tandem catalysts, which, in combination with theoretical calculations, will lead to the underpinning of the reaction mechanism and allow the rational improvement of the nanostructured catalysts to achieve an industry-relevant level of performance.

Building on the consortium's know-how, the catalysts will be deployed in a membrane reactor featuring a combination of tailored nanocomposite membranes, giving access to ethylene in a selective manner and high yield for the first time.

The MemCat science-to-technology breakthrough will be achieved through a synergy of synthesis, catalysis, and theory to obtain novel nanostructured tandem catalysts, and the development of nanocomposite membranes for a prototype catalytic membrane reactor, replacing current multi-step conversion pathways with existing catalysts.

The long-term vision of MemCat is to give access to green e-Polymers by providing carbon-negative plastic precursors using anthropogenic CO₂ and green H₂.

The project will contribute to establishing the EU as the world leader in the use of CO₂ as feedstock for chemical production.

[Objectives](#)

[Expected results](#)

[Long term impact](#)

Figure 3. About us Section

The MemCat Consortium involves various partners, including universities, research organizations, and an SME, working together in different work packages (WPs). Key interactions focus on nanomaterial synthesis, catalytic investigations, computational modelling, and membrane development.

Meet the Partners:

> LABORATORIO IBERICO INTERNACIONAL DE NANOTECNO

Established in 2009, the International Iberian Nanotechnology Laboratory (INL) is a collaborative research and...

[Read more](#)

> JYVASKYLAN YLIOPISTO

The University of Jyväskylä (JYU) is an internationally recognized multidisciplinary research institution dedicated to...

[Read more...](#)

Figure 4. Partners Section

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2.3 News

A dedicated page shows the latest updates from the project. Here, the latest news of the project will be provided to communicate the major achievements of the research, internal meetings or other relevant information related to MemCat project. This will enable to spread out news through different channels and build a better presence of the website in the search engines.

Last News

by 1 Cube / on June 28, 2024

1st May 2024 OFFICIAL START of the project! 🎉

Message from our coordinator [Yury V. Kolen'ko](#)

"A warm welcome to our joint [hashtag#MemCathashtag#project](#), which has just started yesterday on such a significant May 1 – [hashtag#Labour](#) Day 😊

I am sure that our next 4 years will be filled with opportunities, events, and exciting new research."

Membrane-assisted Ethylene Synthesis over Nanostructured Tandem Catalysts | MemCat | Project | Fact sheet | HORIZON | CORDIS | European Commission ([europa.eu](#))

WRITTEN BY

1 Cube

LEAVE A COMMENT

Figure 5. News Section

2.4 Events

This section will include a list of events that the consortium will organise and in which they will participate, as conferences and workshops.

The screenshot shows the MEMCAT website's Events section. At the top is a navigation bar with the MEMCAT logo and menu items: Home, About MemCat, News, Events (underlined), Project Results, Dissemination, and Contact. Below the navigation bar is a large teal banner with the word "EVENTS" centered. Underneath the banner, there are three identical placeholder cards, each featuring a laurel wreath icon and the text "COMING SOON". Below the banner is a "PROJECT DETAILS" section. On the left, it lists: Project number: 101130047; Project name: Membrane-assisted Ethylene Synthesis over Nanostructured Tandem Catalysts; Project acronym: MemCat; Call: HORIZON-EIC-2023-PATHFINDEROPEN-01; Topic: HORIZON-EIC-2023-PATHFINDEROPEN-01-01. On the right, it lists: Duration: 48 months; EU funding: € 3 867 841,25; Project Coordinator: Yury V. Kolen'ko. At the bottom right of the details section is the text: COORDINATOR: LABORATORIO IBERICO INTERNACIONAL DE NANOTECNOLOGIA LIN. To the right of the project details is a logo for the European Union with the text "Funded by the European Union".

Figure 6. Events section

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2.5 Project Results

This section will include articles, publications as well as other results stemming from the project work.

MEMCAT Home About MemCat News Events Project Results Dissemination Contact

PROJECT RESULTS

COMING SOON COMING SOON COMING SOON

PROJECT DETAILS

Project number: 101130047

Project name: Membrane-assisted Ethylene Synthesis over Nanostructured Tandem Catalysts

Project acronym: MemCat

Call: HORIZON-EIC-2023-PATHFINDEROPEN-01

Topic: HORIZON-EIC-2023-PATHFINDEROPEN-01-01

Duration: 48 months

EU funding: € 3 867 841,25

Project Coordinator: Yury V. Kolen'ko

COORDINATOR: LABORATORIO IBERICO INTERNACIONAL DE NANOTECNOLOGIA LIN

Funded by the European Union

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Figure 7. Project results section

2.6 Dissemination

In this section, we will showcase promotional materials of the MemCat project, including videos, webinars, newsletters, and information about participants attending events and conferences. Additionally, all printed materials will be included. A dedicated subpage has been created for the different types of dissemination materials.

Figure 8. Dissemination Section

2.7 Analytics

To monitor the activity of the website, an analytics report can be created to analyse the main trends and statistics. This includes number of visits, visitor's countries, number of users, devices used to visit the website, etc. By performing periodic checks of these indicators, strategies to reach a wider and wider public and raise public awareness can be implemented during the MemCat project.

3. Project Logo

The logotype is the cornerstone of MemCat's brand and design framework. The idea was to develop a logo from scratch that was modern, edgy and related with the areas of the project, and that included scientific elements related to the project. Three key words were selected for this: ethylene, black Co₂ and green H₂. Based on them and the colours selected, 17 project logos were created by 1CUBE. They were shared with the project leader, Yury Kolenko, to select 2 of them.

Figure 9. The initial logos created

A doodle was created for partners to vote for the one they preferred. This was the final logo selected:

Figure 10. MemCat logo

4. Social Media Links

To efficiently reach the targets for dissemination and to maximise the visibility of the project, its activities and results, four social media channels are being used for the MemCat project: LinkedIn, Youtube, Facebook and Instagram. Links to them have been placed in the MemCat website (see Figure 11 below). A X account (formerly Twitter) will be created later on in the project. By leveraging these platforms effectively, MemCat aims to enhance its outreach efforts, engage a diverse audience, and ensure the project's objectives are widely disseminated and supported.

Figure 11. Social media accounts links in MemCat website